

BB-2208

Human Resource Management

Individual Assignment 2

Chosen company: Syarikat Al Rasyid

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Executive summary

Human Resource Management is had been proven to be one of the must have unit in a company. An HRM model should also be designed or a company can use an existing HRM model. Syarikat Al Rasyid a growing agriculture business that encounter problems that may concern Human Resource Management. So, the Guest model of HRM was suggested as it is a strategic approach to managing human capital. However, there are other solutions proposed in contrary to the use of HRM models. Using an HRM model have its very own advantages and disadvantages which is analysed in this report for the Guest model of HRM.

Introduction

Human Resource Management is one of the vital operations in an organization as it hires people with differing skills into the company. The Human Resource department is undoubtedly in place for every company that have contributed to a positive result. When the human capital in the company is properly managed or allocated, efficiency can be achieved which improve company's market value. This department is also responsible to further improve employees' skills and to retain the right people in the company.

For Human Resource Management specifically in the agriculture sector, Human Resource Managers will have to recruit workers with a desired skill by the company to work in agriculture business. As the operation in agriculture sector requires a skill for different tasks, managers must assess their workers' expertise to assign them in the right job for their abilities. So, there is quite a lot of models of Human Resource Management that can be adopted by companies to organize their human capital. These models are readily made to help Human Resource Managers to plan on how their human capital is going to be used to optimize results of their companies.

Human Resource Management model is an organization strategic plan that is intended to help design business activities within the company with the use of human capital. As the goal is to assist companies to properly manage their human resource to utilize them effectively and to achieve efficiency in their tasks that is aligned with the company's objectives. There is a concept where Human Resource Management have two approaches of managing their workforce, which are the hard HRM and soft HRM. These approaches have distinctive characteristics in how employees are treated and utilized to finish their tasks. Firstly, the hard HRM heavily focuses on employees' performance while disregarding the well-being of their employees, treating them as machines and it also uses incentives to motivate them. Lastly, the soft HRM focuses on trusting their employees and they believe that employees are an asset to the company where they treat them as individuals. Most Human Resource Management model have a mix of these two approaches.

Syarikat Al Rasyid

Syarikat Al Rasyid is an agriculture business that is focusing on the paddy cultivation, which is owned by Muhammad Abdul Rasyid bin Kamarudjaman and registered on 4th of October 2016. Syarikat Al Rasyid have a 1 hectare land located in MPK Kampung Bebuloh where the

operation of paddy farming is started. The owner of Syarikat Al-Rasyid first started his paddy farming in 2015 after completing the Kursus Belia Berpadi course. Rasyid, the owner of Syarikat Al Rasyid is one of the four individuals that received the Usahawan Belia Aktif award for the 'Projek Perintis Menggalakan Para Belia Menceburi Pengeluaran Padi Negara' category in 2017.

During the 2017, Rasyid and two of his friends were selected to take part in the 'Hybrid Rice Comprehensive Technology of Developing Countries' course in China. The course taught participants on the hybrid paddy cultivation and develop skills to use the technology. In addition, Rasyid also went on a mentorship from well-established paddy businesses. Under their mentorship, Rasyid had utilized the knowledge he had learn to run his own farm.

Problems of Syarikat Al Rasyid

There are a lot of issues in Syarikat Al Rasyid, one of them is to finance resources of the farm as the government only supplied them with land. Favorably, LiveWIRE had given Rasyid \$15,000 as a start-up capital for his farm. Rasyid is also financially supported by his family to cover his expenses. Without the help of his family, he will have to make a bank loan or even look for investors to his company.

But that is the lesser of the issue faced by Syarikat Al Rasyid, the major issue was the land provided by the Government, it was impossible to cultivate paddy as the land was not fertile. To solve this issue, Rasyid had to do manual labor for long hours which in turn it greatly affects his rice production.

Due to poor infrastructure in the area of the farm, managing the cultivation and accessing it was burdensome. This could make the transporting of resources longer. To add more, clean water used for the farm are shared amongst farmers, so sometimes the farmers only depend on the rain to water their cultivation.

Guest model of HRM

There are several Human Resource Management models that can be adopted which one of it is the Guest model of Human Resource Management. This model is designed by David Guest back in the 1987. Guest model of HRM is centered on the soft approach of HRM while also using hard approach of HRM and created to build a commitment-based organization.

Moreover, this model's assumption is that before appointing employees to a job, the Human Resource Managers need to have their Human Resource strategies planned and create practices that when it is performed, will produce outcomes. It also shows that Human Resource Management and Personnel Management differs from each other. There are 6 dimensions of analysis introduced in this model which are Human Resource Strategy, Human Resource practices, Human Resource outcomes, behavioral outcomes, performance outcomes and financial outcomes.

Guest model highly emphasize that Human Resource Management and Personnel Management are different. To show that Human Resource Management and Personnel Management are different is by using commitment-based HRM (Human Resource Management) and compliance-based HRM (Personnel Management) as perceived by Guest. In a compliance-based HRM, employees of the company are set to comply with the policies, rules and standards established. Within a compliance-based HRM, there is a low-level of trust between the organization and employees where employees are controlled to finish tasks using the set standard. In contrast, in a commitment-based HRM, employees are valued as to they are intended to be involved reaching the organization's strategy and goals. This in turn provides a high level of trust between organization and employees which increase the involvement of the employees. In addition, employees are motivated to contribute to the company.

Relating back to the case of Syarikat Al Rasyid there seems to be no HRM model in place to help Rasyid allocate human capital. However, Syarikat Al Rasyid can start to adopt Guest model of HRM to aid the business to solve issues.

Solutions and alternative solutions

With Syarikat Al Rasyid given \$15,000 by LiveWIRE to start the farm business, it will not help the company in the long run. There will be a big gap of a difference in competition with other companies in the agriculture industry when Syarikat Al Rasyid is behind financially. This in turn will have to force Syarikat Al Rasyid to find investors.

For the poor infrastructure in the area of the farm, agriculture business will be badly affected and further development of the agriculture industry will be stagnant or even become worst. The Government should take initiatives to fund the infrastructure in the agriculture businesses as His Majesty had highlighted that the country needs to stop heavily relying on imports for the country's sustainability.

Syarikat Al Rasyid can also hire HR professionals to help manage workers in the company and also implement the Guest model of HRM. There will be a possible increase in efficiency in the workers' work. Using the Guest model of HRM which it needs the managers to construct an HRM strategy to design policies that works for Syarikat Al Rasyid.

After the implementation of Guest model in Syarikat Al Rasyid, he or a Human Resource Manager hired by him can start a meeting about the HRM strategy that is to be established within the company. A Human Resource strategy is the general plan of an organization that is aligned with the business strategy. A good strategy can give an organization a competitive advantage in the industry. An HRM strategy that can be used is cost reduction strategy, where during a hiring process the manager should reconsider the skills of an individual that will be useful for tasks in an agriculture business. Reduced costs can provide the company with extra capital that can be invested in the development of the business.

Another HRM strategy will be a delegation of work between employees. Employees will have one duty to focus on so that there is a development of skills for the employee, this also will increase efficiency and increase the productivity levels.

After the HRM strategy comes the designing of the HR practices such as hiring, training and development and compensation. Managers hiring process needs to be a selective hiring to add value to the company by hiring the right employee. It is cost-effective to bring in employee that is the right fit for the job and it is also a key to gain a competitive advantage in the industry. Syarikat Al Rasyid can create this practice so that to improve their competitive advantage and also reduce the cost burden of the company, as Rasyid is currently financially supported by his family, this could also stop his family financial aid on his company so that they can use the money somewhere that may benefit them. This is aligned with the suggested cost-reduction strategy to help save money for the company's well-being.

The second HR practice is the training and development. This is where organizations should try to invest its budget more on. After finishing the selective hiring process, the company need to ensure that the employees they recruited is equipped with a proper skill to gain competitive advantage and increase productivity levels. In the agriculture business, it needs a specialized skill in technology used to farm these cultivations. Without a skill, the planting of these farm may end up terribly, it will slow down the production and the company's growth of profit will be affected. This is why it is important for a company to invest time in training and development of employees. Syarikat Al Rasyid should definitely implement this practice and invest time on

it. Rasyid have been through many courses that helped him to obtain these agricultural skills, this also can reduce the cost of hiring outsiders or funding these employees into an agriculture course to train them. Although, it takes time to train and develop employees' skills, it is worth it in the long run as mistakes can be minimized by a lot once employees are armed with appropriate skills and ready to plow through the farm in scorching sun. Rasyid now can delegate tasks to employees that fits with the skills that they gained, this will create efficiency, will certainly increase production and most importantly create higher trust level in the company. The maintenance to consistently fertilize the land can now be made in less time.

The third HR practice is compensating employees. In order to retain the right employee, managers need to compensate on their hard work as these employees are valuable to the company. This also will motivate them to put on more effort and increase output to receive compensation. Syarikat Al Rasyid should apply this practice. To help the company flourish, the human capital in it should be compensated to avoid them from leaving the company and possibly the good employee leaving. However, equity in compensating these employees should also be considered, sometimes the best performing employee may feel their effort is not appreciated in the company with the below-average pay and leave. Human resource is the most valuable resource in every company, so Syarikat Al Rasyid need to do their best in compensating their employees fairly.

In Guest model, after the HR practices comes the outcome after the execution of these practices. The possible outcomes from the practices suggested are the employees are more committed to stay in the company, quality of the product will improve and a higher trust level between employee and organization. Following these practices could also encourage involvement from employee by the organization that can reduce absenteeism and lower the labor turnover rate. In the financial side, the growth in profit can be expected.

Advantages and disadvantages of using Guest model of HRM

Human Resource models have their very own advantage and disadvantage. With the application of Guest model of HRM in Syarikat Al Rasyid will produce its advantage and disadvantage depending on how it is executed or planned. For it to be successful, the planning of the HRM strategy is to be prioritized before designing the HR practices. Nonetheless, in the end it all depends on the execution of the model.

Advantages:

The advantages will be mostly derived from the outcomes. Higher commitment of employee to the company, higher level of trust, encouraging employees to be involved and it could reduce cost. A better management of human capital for the company.

Disadvantages:

This model requires manager to focus on the strategy and practices developed in the company. When managers are too focused on the strategies, they may overlook other good factors to be revised in the strategy or even other helping factors out of the Human Resource field. Development of the Human Resource Department may be stagnant.

Conclusion

Syarikat Al Rasyid should still find a way to solve their problem through other options. There are many models that can be used to manage human resource or make their own model of HRM that fit perfectly for their company. Nonetheless, using the Guest model of HRM will still benefit them as this model emphasize a strategic approach to managing human capital to lessen the chance of failure. An HR practices such as selective hiring, training and development and compensation is considered to be one of the best combination of practices that can be used in Syarikat Al Rasyid. Thus, it is definitely recommended for Syarikat Al Rasyid to implement this model in the company.

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